

Research Questionnaire: Generative Artificial Intelligence in Software Engineering

1 Personal and Professional Profile

1. Gender: *

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- Other: _____

2. What is your age group? *

- 18 to 24 years old
- 25 to 34 years old
- 35 to 44 years old
- 45 to 54 years old
- 55 to 64 years old
- 65 years old or older

3. Educational Level: *

- Incomplete High School
- Complete High School
- Incomplete Higher Education
- Complete Higher Education
- Incomplete Specialization/MBA
- Complete Specialization/MBA
- Incomplete Master's Degree
- Complete Master's Degree
- Incomplete Doctoral Degree

- Complete Doctoral Degree

4. Location: * Provide the name of the city and the state/country abbreviation. (e.g., Curitiba/PR - Brazil)

5. What is the segment of the company you work for? *

- Agribusiness and Agriculture
- Industry and Manufacturing
- Civil Construction and Engineering
- Transportation and Logistics
- Wholesale and Retail Trade
- Food and Beverages
- Health and Wellness
- Education and Training
- Information Technology and Software
- Telecommunications and Internet
- Energy and Utilities (water, gas, electricity)
- Financial Services (banks, fintechs, insurance, accounting)
- Tourism, Hospitality, and Events
- Entertainment, Culture, and Sports
- Legal Services and Consulting
- Real Estate and Urbanism
- Public and Government Services
- Non-profit Organizations / NGO
- Other: _____

6. What role do you currently hold? *

- Executive/IT Leadership: CIO, CTO, Director, IT Manager, Technology Coordinator
- Project/Product Management: Project Manager, Product Owner, Scrum Master, Project Analyst, Agile Coach, PMO

- Software Engineering/Development: Back-end, Front-end, Full Stack Developer, Software Engineer
- Requirements Engineering/Business Analysis: Requirements Analyst, Business Analyst, Product Analyst
- Experience and Interface Design: UX Designer, UI Designer, Product Designer, Service Designer
- Software/Solutions Architecture: Software Architect, Solutions Architect, System Designer, Tech Lead
- Quality and Testing: QA Engineer, Test Analyst, Quality Engineer, Automation Tester
- Infrastructure/Operations/DevOps: SysAdmin, DevOps Engineer, SRE, Cloud Engineer, Network Administrator
- Database and Data: DBA, Data Engineer, Data Analyst, Data Scientist, BI Analyst
- Information Security: Security Analyst, CISO, Pentester, Cybersecurity Specialist
- Technical Support and Field Service: Help Desk, Service Desk, Field Service, Support Analyst, Field Technician
- IT Consulting/Training: Technology Consultant, Instructor, Technical Facilitator
- Other: _____

7. Years of experience in the technology field: *

- Less than 1 year
- 1 to 5 years
- 5 to 10 years
- 10 to 15 years
- More than 15 years

8. Size of the organization you work for: *

- Micro (up to 19 employees)
- Small (up to 99 employees)
- Medium (up to 499 employees)
- Large (over 499 employees)

2 Application of Generative AI

9. When you use Generative AI at work, which of the options below best describes the type of result you seek and the means? *

Objective / Scenario	Comm. tool	AI-based tool	AI-based framework	Not Applicable
Generate artifacts (texts, documentation, models, specifications, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Testing generation/support	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Development-related tasks (generate, complete, refactor)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Task automation (scripts, routines, integrations)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other scenarios	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If you checked "Other scenarios", describe which specific applications and means you use in your daily routine. Otherwise, answer only "Not selected". *

10. In which stages of software engineering is Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) used in your professional practice? *

(Check all options that apply. The phases follow the Software Engineering Body of Knowledge - SWEBOK)

- Software Requirements - elicit and refine requirements from vague demands, analyze and negotiate scope, prioritize backlog, specify functional and non-functional requirements, validate understanding, manage changes and traceability.
- Software Architecture gather technical and business drivers, define architectural styles, patterns, and tactics, model architecture views, capture decisions (ADRs), assess impacts, and govern solution evolution.
- Software Design - model components, interfaces, and data, apply design principles and patterns, design UI/APIs, detail solutions for implementation and testing.
- Software Construction - code functionalities, review code, integrate components, automate builds and pipelines, manage dependencies, perform profiling and optimizations.
- Software Testing - plan and design test cases, automate suites, execute functional and non-functional tests, manage defects and metrics, report results.
- Software Engineering Operations - plan releases, orchestrate deploys and rollbacks, monitor systems (observability), work with DevOps/SRE (SLIs/SLOs), handle incidents, and conduct post-mortems.

- Software Maintenance - perform corrective, adaptive, perfective, and preventive corrections, analyze change impact, refactor code, manage technical debt, and update documentation.
- Software Configuration Management - version code and artifacts, control changes (branch/merge, baselines), perform audits, ensure build traceability, and manage artifacts and SBOM.
- Software Engineering Management - plan activities and estimations, manage risks and resources, monitor key performance indicators (KPIs), communicate with stakeholders, and record lessons learned.
- Software Engineering Process - define and adapt processes, measure, audit, and improve practices (SPI), establish governance and compliance gates, support training and adoption.
- Software Engineering Models and Methods - choose life cycle models (agile, incremental, DevOps), apply methods and modeling (UML, BPMN, DDD), prototype, experiment, and apply MDE.
- Software Quality - define quality goals (e.g., ISO/IEC 2510), plan QA/QC and V&V, monitor metrics and dashboards, conduct audits and reviews, support continuous improvement.
- Software Security - perform threat modeling, define security and privacy requirements, apply secure coding (OWASP), execute testing (SAST/DAST), manage vulnerabilities, and implement DevSecOps practices.
- Professional Practice - technical communication and leadership, teamwork, knowledge management and sharing, mentoring, and continuous development.
- Software Economics - analyze cost-benefit and ROI, perform estimations, make-or-buy decisions, prioritize portfolio by value, and make decisions under uncertainty.
- Computing Foundations - apply concepts of operating systems, networks and databases, data structures and algorithms, concurrency, distributed systems, and cloud computing.
- Mathematical Foundations - apply logic and sets, probability and statistics, graphs and optimization, calculus and numerical methods, foundation for formal verification.
- Engineering Foundations - apply principles of systems engineering, reliability and safety, measurement, modeling and simulation, risk management, and technical standards.
- I don't know
- Other: _____

11. Which Generative AI tools, APIs, or models do you use in your daily professional routine? How do you typically use them? *

Include the name of the tool/LLM and briefly describe its use. Examples: "ChatGPT to generate and review documentation", "GitHub Copilot to complete and refactor code", etc.

12. Do you use Generative Artificial Intelligence to create new content or artifacts in your work? *

- Do not use
- Generate source code (functions, classes, scripts, snippets)
- Create technical documentation (e.g., API guides, user manuals, system documentation)
- Write test cases or QA scenarios
- Produce requirements specifications or user stories
- Generate data models, diagrams, or process flows
- Suggest initial solution ideas for technical problems
- Create interface prototypes or mockups
- Draft technical outlines or report drafts
- Other: _____

13. Do you use Generative Artificial Intelligence to share or disseminate information in your work? *

- Do not use
- Create automatic summaries of meetings, documents, or emails
- Generate FAQs or support guides for teams
- Translate documentation into other languages
- Organize AI outputs into centralized repositories/documentation
- Produce automated presentations or reports for stakeholders
- Support the communication of best practices within the team
- Reuse knowledge generated by AI across different teams/projects
- Produce internal training content (e.g., tutorials, checklists)
- Other: _____

14. Is Generative Artificial Intelligence used to directly apply to daily work? *

- Not used
- Use generated code in real production systems
- Apply suggested fixes for bugs or vulnerabilities
- Support architecture or software design decisions
- Support code reviews (AI-assisted code review)
- Automate repetitive tasks (e.g., deploy scripts, automated tests)
- Improve existing code quality (refactoring)
- Analyze logs, metrics, or data for decision-making
- Support effort or deadline estimations for projects
- Generate documentation from code currently in use
- Support maintenance or sustenance activities (e.g., automated responses, troubleshooting)
- Other: _____

15. In what ways does Artificial Intelligence help (or not) you to create, share, and use information and insights in your work? *

16. Now, in general, how is Generative Artificial Intelligence most applied within your team or organization? *

- Exchange of experiences between people: (e.g., summarizing documents, consolidating data from different systems, creating integrated reports or dashboards, answering questions based on multiple sources)
- Transforming ideas into materials or documents: (e.g., generating technical documentation, creating manuals, drafting meeting summaries or specifications from conversations)
- Gathering and reorganizing already recorded information: (e.g., summarizing documents, consolidating data from different systems, creating integrated reports or dashboards, answering questions based on multiple sources)
- Supporting learning and practical application: (e.g., suggesting code improvements, recommending best practices, generating tutorials, helping with training in new languages or tools)
- None of the options
- Other: _____

17. We would love to hear your opinion! Based on your current work or previous professional experiences, how do you view the use of Generative Artificial Intelligence? *

If possible, tell us about: Applications you have seen or imagine; Perceived gains or benefits (e.g., more agility, quality, cost reduction); Other relevant points, such as challenges, cautions, or ideas for improvement.
